

THE INVESTIGATION OF THE TERMS OF LOGISTICS

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Abstract: This article analysis the research structure of terms related to logistics that plays an important role in defining logistics, and reveals the phenomenon that combines different meanings. The existence of language processes in the field of logistic terminology naturally proves that terms are treated as units of language. The existence of these semantic processes allows a better understanding of the relationship of terms in the system and the content of terminology.

Key words: *term and terminology, logistic terminology, language units, investigation, linguistics, language meaning, definition, transport logistics*

Over the past decade, the description and analysis of scientific and technical term systems has become one of the leading areas of research in the field of linguistics. The interest in specific terminology issues is explained by the growing importance of terminology and its various directions in the field of standardization. The process of regulating the scientific and technical level in many respects, it is important to conduct research in the field of linguistics, aimed at eliminating inconsistencies between language and special-scientific fields, as well as language barriers encountered in special-professional activities. In particular, the study of the terminology of transport logistics from a young perspective from a linguistic point of view determines its relevance around the world.

In the English and Uzbek terminology system of transport logistics, there is a semantic connection between the meanings of polysemous terms. If such a connection is weak or absent, then terms with a homonymous character may

represent a semantic relationship. Homonyms are lexical units that have the same, different meanings in spelling and reading.

According to lexicological and lexicographic classifications, the following aspect of homonymy is often recognized, including that “homonyms are always words in different forms and only in the course of historical development have words with equal phonetic and matching speech sounds for different phonetic and usually random reasons. In addition, ways of word formation and forms of syntactic adaptation are important for distinguishing polysemy and homonymy. Thus, when a polysemous word is denied to consist of two or more lexical units, it is necessary to recognize units with the same speech sound belonging to different parts of speech, for example:

Back:

- 1) Noun phrase: *back (bel)*
- 2) Adverb: *back, the opposite side (qarama - qarshi tomonga, orqaga)*
- 3) Adjective: *back, next (orqadagi, keyingisi)*
- 4) Verb: *support (qo'llab-quvvatlash)*

Such words belong to different grammatical categories and have different syntactic and lexical valences. In this case, it is not possible to express different parts of speech in one word. This approach does not allow for clarification and strict demarcation of the concepts of polysemy and homonymy.

In the semantic structure of terms, semantic homonymy is formed as a result of separating the meaning of the term or transferring the name to another concept, while retaining the general basic semantics. If homonymy is studied more deeply within a particular aspect such as a term homonymy, there is common meaning, although the meanings of a single term used in different terminology systems are radically different from each other. According to some linguists, only a state of homonymy has been observed when used in practice in different term systems or in languages with relatively few speakers. Considering the different variants of terminological homonymy, it should be noted that there are three types of homonymous relations and types of *terminological homonymy*:

1) Intersystem (macro systemic) homonymy between units of terminological and general literary systems;

2) Intersystem (interdisciplinary) homonymy between different term system units;

3) Internal system homonymy between term system units.

Hence, in terminology, homonymy is considered as one of its features. 1.5% of the existing ones in the English and Uzbek transport logistics terminology system are homonymous terms. Logistics has close ties with areas such as transportation, container and packaging, marketing, management, sales, law. Thus the homonymous terms appear. If we refer to the terms with such homonymous properties:

Tube:

1. Soft tuba (*yumshoq truba*): this term is derived from the term "packaging" and means "one-sided, soft packaging";

2. Tunnel (tunel): architectural structure - a terminal of a certain type of underground transport. The term is also used to mean "metro", especially for the London Underground; **Car:**

a. Automobile (car terminology);

b. Subway/underground (railway terminology).

In many cases, the meaning of the term is determined by the context. As for terminological antonymy, as some linguists have acknowledged that the phenomenon of antonymy serves to maximize the enrichment of the lexical layer of language at the level of literary language. It should be noted that the antonymic feature of special lexemes shows the importance of the aspect that allows to determine the position of terminological units in the system, that is, to classify them. There are 52 pairs of antonyms in the English transport logistics terminology system, and the following aspects of these term-antonyms have been identified:

1) A pair of term-antonyms is often a stem represented by component terminological units:

Accept (refusal to supply goods). One-component core antonyms are rare occurs in cases: loading - unloading;

Conveyable (on a conveyor belt moving materials);

Non-conveyable (on a conveyor belt) immovable materials;

2) species representing antonymic relations are represented by complementary antonyms:

Heavy cargo - balloon cargo;

a) Conversion antonyms (changing roles): buyer (seller “sotuvchi”) - customer (buyer “xaridor”); consignor (sender of goods “jo’natuvchi”) - customer (receiver “qabul qiliuvchi”);

b) Vector antonyms (according to location): head (poyezdning bosh qismi) - tail (poyezdning tugalliq qismi); port of discharge (kirish porti)

c) Antonyms denoting the opposite quality: high (baland) - low (past).

Also, lexical-semantic processes in the system of terms related to transport logistics are observed in the following cases:

1) The term is not a specific word, but a word that performs a special function, so lexical and semantic processes in literary language are specific to terminological units;

2) There are some requirements to the term - unambiguousness, methodological neutrality, the absence of synonyms, and so on. Nowadays, this requirement is considered to be a specific aspect of the term that cannot always be realized in simple communication. It is natural, therefore, that lexical and semantic processes exist in term systems;

3) The presence of polysemy, homonymy and antonyms in transport logistics indicates its systemicity;

4) Polysemous words related to transport logistics make up almost 1% of this term system, lexemes with homonymous character - 1.5% and term-antonyms - 0.5%. These indicators indicate that most of the lexemes meet the requirements for terminological units.

This article is devoted to the study of the semantic method of construction of logistics terms and develops the following theoretical aspects: the definition of the term "term" is given and its multifaceted nature is revealed; analysis of the terminological structure of the logistics of English and Uzbek languages; the main difficulties in translating logistics terms were identified, the most effective ways of solving them were identified; methods of translating terms were studied and logistics the most acceptable and common of them in terms of terminology detected. The main problem in achieving the equivalence of the translation of texts in the scientific and business style is to illuminate the original content of the text using the terminological system of the translated language. The difference between the source language and the terminological systems of the target language causes the greatest difficulties in translation. This implies the need to study terminological systems and find ways to translate partially equivalent and non-equivalent phrases.

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